

Mobilizing Social Capital to Overcome Corona Disasters

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Indonesia is in the emergency response condition of the corona virus pandemic non natural disaster (Covid-19). Corona continues to plague its distribution in almost all regions. The number of confirmed cases, in treatment, until death continues to increase every day.

At present Indonesia is still in a crisis. It is this crisis handling that will determine whether the number of positive corona cases will continue to rise or be controlled. Indonesia may have a lot of experience in handling natural disasters. But handling non-natural disasters such as the corona virus, Indonesia is a beginner. Although during the Dutch East Indies period, a similar disaster caused by the Spanish flu outbreak, in fact the health history was no more interesting than the history of politics.

Law No. 24 of 2007 concerning Disaster Management states that epidemics and epidemics are examples of non-natural disasters. Currently Indonesia is in the emergency response period, after ignoring the corona disaster risk reduction, when it is endemic in many countries. In fact, corona becomes the official joke, so sad.

However it is never too late to inhibit and stop the spread of the corona. Facing the disaster of the invisible creature, President Joko Widodo said community solidarity is the capital to fight it. Community solidarity can move the Indonesian people together against Covid-19. Finally, social capital is expected to be a social weapon to overcome the corona disaster.

A decade ago, the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) conducted a measurement of social capital to determine the stock of social capital in Indonesia (BPS, 2010). Measuring instruments that refer to the World Bank instruments (Grootaert *et al.*, 2004) are still relevant for driving social energy to overcome corona disasters. Following is the implementation of several social capital subdimensions in the context of building a collective movement to overcome the corona disaster.

Strengthening Groups and Networks

Indonesian people are accustomed to living in communal life both formally and informally. The group is one of the important social capital in Indonesia. The power of groups can encourage togetherness to solve problems, including corona disasters. Group participation is needed to build collective strength against the plague.

Building individual awareness in community groups is important to break the chain of distribution of corona. Here, the role of *opinion leader is needed* to build awareness and change behavior to support the corona disaster management. For example, remind each other to obey the protocol to prevent the spread of viruses to the smallest RT / RW environment.

In addition, the group's role is to strengthen the community's mental immunity so as not to experience an outbreak of *anxiety* due to corona.

Furthermore, networks between groups must be strengthened to build greater strength. Remove the flag and social, cultural, religious identity, and so on. Network groups without barriers and boundaries will more effectively unite a variety of different interests for the same interest: overcoming the corona disaster. The network formed will build collective solidarity, as President Jokowi wants.

Mutual Trust and Solidarity

An attitude of mutual trust is needed to overcome the corona disaster. Mutual trust is needed both between communities and with policy makers. The community must believe in the corona's disaster management policy scheme, while still thinking critically. Believe when asked to stay at home, work at home, eliminate crowded activities, not crowding, and so on to prevent massive spread of the virus.

Without public trust, the government's efforts to overcome the corona disaster will be in vain. Vice versa, the government must believe that people also do not stay silent. The community is helping, either by simply following the government's advice, or helping to overcome the lack of equipment and needs that the government has not been able to meet. For example the need for medical personnel, masks, *hand sanitizers*, food ingredients, and others.

The government should maintain this trust by optimizing the Corona disaster management efforts. Prioritizing the interests of the public over the interests of a handful of elites.

Trust will foster solidarity, both individually and collectively. Solidarity is social energy to face the corona disaster. Solidarity among citizens can build strength at the community level. Political solidarity to build political power and policy at the country level. In the event of a disaster, eliminate the barriers of rulers and opposition: national solidarity is more important.

Mutual Cooperation and Cooperation

Mutual cooperation is a social capital that has taken root, the heritage of Indonesia's ancestors. The participation of individuals and groups is needed to overcome disasters. Forget political feuds to cope with disasters and ensure collective safety. Instead of commenting and blaming each other, citizens and political elites should intervene to move their groups to get involved in disaster management together.

Cooperation is also needed from business actors not to take advantage of the situation by raising unnatural prices and hoarding goods. The business world should be responsive in allocating CSR funds for Corona disaster management. In such conditions, all can be victims. If the business world does not want to take part, the business in the future will be disrupted. Because the business world is related to HR and markets. Both are driven by humans. And, corona outbreaks target humans, anyone, anywhere.

Information and Communication

This dimension plays an important role in overcoming infodemic epidemics on various social media. WHO explains, infodemic is a wave of excessive information about a problem, which then makes it difficult to identify the solution. In this case, the virtual virus is often a trigger for noise on social media. This information can actually be more dangerous than the corona pandemic itself. Hoaks one of them.

The massive spread of hoaxes related to corona will trigger public panic and disrupt the national socioeconomic system. Just see when the rupiah reaches its lowest point, conversations on social media actually trigger a commotion not solutive. The hashtag war is still going on between the colors of the pros and cons of the government.

Hoaks can also occur in the real world at the community level, triggering *panic buying* in traditional markets. Faced with this, government officials in the regions up to the village / kelurahan level should be able to become communicators for the community. In crisis conditions, citizens need communicators whose sources can be trusted.

The *covid19.go.id* site is an attempt to ward off infodemics. As of March 27, 2020, there have been 188 hoaks that have been successfully resisted. Even though the reality is like an iceberg phenomenon, corona-related hoaks are still endemic on various social media and messaging applications. There are still many parties whose fingers are more agile than reason who share unverified information.

On the other hand, the government should be more open to infrastructure data and resources to overcome the corona disaster. The gap between government information and field reality causes public distrust. In addition, the public needs accurate information about the individual and the location of the Person in Monitoring (Called ODP), Patient Under Supervision (Called PDP), and positive patient corona, while maintaining the confidentiality of the patient's personal identity.

The Alliance of Independent Journalists (AJI) even made a petition on the *change.org* siteso that the government opens information on the distribution of infections and the travel history of positive patients with Covid-19 Information disclosure as required by AJI is important to create caution and vigilance. Openness of information can make people do risk mitigation independently.

Closed, confusing, and vague information will only create panic or indifference. Many people are still indifferent and relaxed because they feel that the area of residence and

activities are safe from the corona outbreak. Finally, the government's call to stay at home was ignored.

Social Closeness and Togetherness

This dimension relates to social closeness, efforts to reduce conflict as a result of various kinds of differences between community members, as well as the presence or absence of discrimination against access to public services. Social closeness is needed so that the corona disaster does not trigger conflicts, both SARA conflicts, identity conflicts, and economic conflicts.

No doubt, the corona disaster has an impact on the economy of the community, especially the informal sector and MSMEs. Economic problems usually have a domino effect on social problems. Social closeness is needed to reduce the domino effect. In this context, social closeness will be related to economic closeness. Economic closeness will protect the community from potential economic conflicts.

When the government decides on a work-at-home policy, a ban on assembly, a ban on opening a business, should be accompanied by incentives for businesses and informal workers to be affected.

Socio-economic closeness also means that those who are not economically affected help their affected neighbors. The government, community leaders, public figures, and anyone else, should be able to encourage the socio-economic closeness in their environment. The cash / infaq funds for houses of worship should be allocated to the food needs of directly affected communities, until the pandemic ends.

This social and economic closeness will strengthen the togetherness of citizens and the state in overcoming the corona disaster. Together, the Indonesian people will fight to win against the invisible creature. As President Jokowi said, we are a big nation, a warrior nation, a warrior nation, *God willing*, able to face this severe global challenge.

Empowerment and Political Action

Empowerment is needed to manage the community's ability to overcome the corona disaster. Indonesian people have been empowered and tested to overcome the problem of natural disasters in this country. Community empowerment is needed, because they are also subjects, not just policy objects. Facing the corona disaster, the government could not have done it alone, without community participation.

In disaster conditions, community initiatives are needed to overcome problems in their environment. For example, amid the scarcity of masks and *hand sanitizers*, many individuals and communities make these rare items and share them for free to those in need. More than that, there are also distributing groceries to the most economically affected communities.

These initiatives need to be developed throughout Indonesia, so that they become a political action for the community. Political action also needs to be moved to encourage state officials to be more sensitive to public interests. It was natural for the public to get

angry, when the political elite wanted him and his family to get the *Corona rapid test* facility. Even though ODP and medical staff are more in need than them.

These various social capital subdimensions need to be applied at various levels, from the micro level, meso level, to the macro level. Application of micro-level social capital at the individual, household or local environment level. Explained by BPS (2010), social capital in the form of groups and networks based on mutual trust and tolerance can overcome various social problems in the local environment.

Policies to stay at home, work at home, not get together, not make a crowd need to be applied at the micro level. Individual motivation with support from family and local environment plays an important role in supporting the policy. The large number of fatalities due to corona in a number of countries in Europe, one of which is due to low social capital at the micro level. When the government makes a policy of staying at home, they ignore it. As a result, victims continue to fall.

This micro level is at the forefront of success or failure of Corona disaster management. The practice of healthy living and preventing the potential for transmission starts from the individual, family, and the surrounding environment. Community leaders at the RW (Hamlet) and RT (Neighbourhood) level should be more proactive in reminding residents to obey the government's call. Religious leaders need to be more rational in worshipping in the midst of an epidemic. For example, inviting worshipers to obey the advice of worship at home.

At the meso level, local governments are expected to optimize the management of the corona disaster by strengthening the task force in the regions, involving all stakeholders. Local governments should also be able to identify and mobilize social capital in their regions. The need for hospitals and personnel and medical equipment in the regions should be addressed by the local government.

Regions should also be able to build emergency laboratories for checking and analysis for ODP and PDP. The quarantine policy of limited areas should also be in the regions.

At the macro level, the central government should allocate the widest possible resources for Corona disaster management, involving all stakeholders, including the business community and civil society. In addition, cooperation with international institutions and between countries needs to be increased for the response to this global pandemic. The non-priority development budget should be allocated for Corona disaster management.

The government is also expected to be more open in providing data and information on the corona case. Information monopoly will only slow down handling. Without transparency, social capital is difficult to mobilize. Public trust in government is key.

As confirmed by BPS (2010), the development of social group capacity depends on the support of the government and the business world. Conversely, the success of government and business world also depends on social stability in society. Socio-economic development can take place well if the government, business world, and civil society create an atmosphere of mutual support for the achievement of common goals. In this case, overcoming the corona disaster. (*)